

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME:** Lawson**FIRST NAME:** Gladys**PROGRAM CODE:** PHGH**COURSE CODE:** ACA-401D**PERIOD NUMBER:** ONE (1)**INSTRUCTOR:** Dr Gulma

Edit or delete text to show actual information below:

The author applied UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

LEARNING THE BASICS OF ACADEMIC WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

As a writer of fiction novels for many years and a scientist, I thought I had a very good understanding of the English language, how to use it and definitely how to write it. As a novelist I have spent copious amounts of time researching various topics for the books I have written and prided myself on being able to take serious issues like human trafficking and teenage suicide and write novels surrounding them that would make a difference and effect positive change. You would think that this would put me in a sphere where I could manipulate the English language and command it on several levels. My first assignment as a PhD student at Euclid University however has shown me that this is far from the truth and that I still have so much to learn about the English language where my academic writing ability is concerned. Not being one to dwell in the status quo and always ready to learn new things I am excited because I know that I am on the pathway to doing something that I have wanted to do for a number of years, my PhD in global health and the tools provided in this coursepack will facilitate this.

2) PERIOD 1 THE COURSEPACK

The 83-page pack of materials for the first period starts with the question ‘What does a good essay need’ (EUCLID 2015, 2)? It then takes one on a journey providing a plethora of rules, suggestions and technical pointers encompassing what is required to write a good essay. I was amazed at the depth and breathe the guidance provided in the coursepack and I found myself delving once again into basic essay writing and all the essential tools required as I did years ago while at University. ‘I am never too old to learn’, is a phrase that I believe in and draw strength from constantly, I used it as I tackled all 83 pages of the material. My first step was comparing American and British

grammar and deciding which I would use (EUCLID 2015, 54-58). I write novels with storylines based in the USA and the UK and tend to use grammar depending on the location of the story however I decided that being a British citizen and educated in the UK, I was going to let British grammar govern my writing and punctuation style.

I have to admit that the placement of the punctuation inside versus outside the quotation marks being assigned to American and British grammar respectively was not something that I was very familiar with (EUCLID, 2015, 59). I found myself trying to recall what I had done when I wrote my MSc thesis and not having a copy to hand, I went online to look at numerous examples of this to familiarise myself. In writing my novels I have tended to place my punctuation inside the quotation marks and did not know that this was a style or particular to American grammar. Knowing that I will be using British grammar I have to ensure that in all my academic writings I place the punctuation outside of the quotation marks.

Plagiarism is something that we are told to avoid when writing papers (EUCLID 2015, 8). A lot of emphasis is placed on plagiarism in the coursepack with examples provided to ensure that students are clear on what it entails (EUCLID 2015, 10). Using someone's work without giving them any credit is an example of plagiarism as is having someone write a paper and putting your name on it (EUCLID 2015, 10). Plagiarism comes with serious consequences and is regarded as a serious academic offence as well as being wrong and unethical (EUCLID 2015, 12). We are told that the best way to avoid plagiarism is to properly cite the author or source that provided the information being used (EUCLID 2015, 13). Citation gives credit to the work or idea of another author. Part of the depth and breathe of the coursepack is evident in the fact that we are provided with ways of how to cite and educated to the fact that there are two types of citation we can use 'in-text citations' and 'list of works cited' (EUCLID 2015, 15).

Quotations and paraphrases are forms of in-text citations (EUCLID 2015, 18). I am reminded that to quote means to use the exact words of the author and to paraphrase is to take the words of an author and reproduce them using your own words. I have experience of using both and found the examples provided in the coursepack very useful.

As an author of fiction novels, I use contractions such as 'can't' and 'don't', instead of 'cannot' and 'do not' in my stories and have done so for years. I find them useful when trying to reduce my word count or for real life-like conversation between my fictional characters. I have learned via the coursepack that I cannot do this when writing academic papers (EUCLID 2015, 39). This means that I have to make sure that I do not get too familiar with my writing that I cross the barrier between fiction and academic writing. In short, I have to be self-aware of my writing. I find myself ready and willing to learn all that I need to achieve success as a Euclid University student, including knowing that I can never use contractions when writing academic papers.

3) STYLES OF ACADEMIC WRITING

EUCLID highlights two major styles of academic writing and requests that its students use them when producing papers. Response Papers are written in the American Psychological Association (APA) style. Major Papers are written in the Chicago Manual of Style, which is a style originated by Kate Turabian (EUCLID 2015, 66).

EUCLID has provided a lot of information about style guides. A style guide is a means of documenting your approach as a writer to certain elements of writing style and needs to be consistent (EUCLID 2015, 52). As a novelist I have not really followed a particular style guide but have always found that my own individual style works well for the story I am telling at the time. In order to be compliant to EUCLID rules I now need to make sure that I follow the APA style for my Response Papers and the Turabian style for my Major Paper.

The preferred length of a sentence, the font usage, spelling (UK versus US), the use of abbreviations, the use of headings and the use of lists are some of the different aspects that can encompass style (EUCLID 2015, 52-53). Consistency is required by EUCLID students. EUCLID recognises the fact that creative writers might not follow a style guide and will use their own. They however have made it clear that they expect students to use a style guide and preferably one that they recommend. They offer help and guidance on writing styles some of which are in the form of websites and others in the form of links. Students are encouraged to download the British Broadcasting Corporation (BBC) News style guide to see how one of the world's foremost news and current affairs organisations handle their style (EUCLID 2015, 53).

Standard American English (SAE) and Standard British English (SBE) are part of the different styles and we are told that American and British English are both variants of World English (EUCLID 2015, 54). A lot of information has been provided about this in the coursepack an example of which is the different spellings but the same pronunciation of certain words. British 'cheque' versus American 'check' are two words which mean the same thing with regards to banking in Britain and America respectively. Aluminium and aluminum are an example of the same term different but similar spelling and pronunciation (EUCLID 2015, 54). There is so much valuable information provided which I have started to grasp and feel that it has already started to change the way I think and write. The coursepack ends with a list of Latin abbreviations and expressions and advises students to always use plain English as well as avoid the use of jargon, acronyms and abbreviations (EUCLID 2005, 78-83). I have used jargon, acronyms and abbreviations to create stories for years however after reading the coursepack I now have a clear distinction in my head that while I can use them in creative writing, I cannot use them in academic writing.

4) CONCLUSION

I have found the information in the coursepack extremely useful. I started reading the material with the knowledge that I had to go through it and produce a paper and I ended up learning a great deal. I now know that academic writing is more technical and structured than creative writing. As a fiction writer I tend to make and break grammatical rules, use contractions and slang whenever I want in order to get my story across to my avid audience. As a pathology manager I have written several reports, Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs) and policies which have not really required a lot of structure. As an academic writer I have to be more structured and consistent in the style that I choose to use and cannot use contractions, bad grammar, jargon or abbreviations. I have written two academic thesis in the past (my BSc and my MSc) but this was a few years ago and I found that the EUCLID coursepack has not only refreshed my mind in academic writing, it has also educated me and given me a better understanding of the level that is required of me as an EUCLID PhD student. The information in the coursepack has motivated me to aim high and now that I have a clearer insight into academic writing I will work hard after all 'I am never too old to learn'.

REFERENCES

Euclid University. 2015. ACA-401 Coursepack: Period 1. Retrieved from: <http://www.eucliduniversity.net/periods/aca-401d-period-1> (accessed 07/12/2019)

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.